

Development of a LW-SMR dry containment model with containmentFOAM

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ABSTRACT

In line with the growing interest in Europe for the deployment of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project launched in 2022 aims to investigate the applicability of the know-how for large-LWRs to water-cooled SMR (LW-SMR). More specifically, the project investigates postulated Severe Accident (SA) sequences for two different “generic” SMRs, Design-I with a submerged containment and Design-II with a dry containment and several passive safety features, based on information available in the open literature. On this basis, the ability of different codes widely used in Europe to analyse the identified SA sequences are evaluated.

This paper presents the up-to-date status of the ‘Design-II’ LW-SMR dry containment model development using containmentFOAM, a CFD package tailored for containment safety analyses based on OpenFOAM-9, which is developed at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ). The use of the code in SASPAM-SA aims to complement the calculations performed with lumped parameter codes, such as MELCOR, ASTEC, or AC2. Due to the close coupling of the containment and the reactor cooling phenomena, the additional insights of containmentFOAM for the buoyancy-driven transport processes and the condensation in presence of non-condensable gases are relevant for the system response. However, the new safety concepts that are feasible due to the reduced size of SMR containments come with novel challenges for the code.

The first priority of the modelling process is to ensure a consistent definition of the model geometry, as it is based on a database conceived for lumped parameter models. The evaluation of the thermal-hydraulic conditions predicted by the lumped parameter codes motivates a review of the applicability of the code to the expected higher pressures and steam concentrations (fluid properties, condensation regimes, etc.). Besides, the liquid released from the reactor vessel occupies a significantly larger fraction of the smaller containment volume. Therefore, two-phase models are currently being tested to consider the more prominent role of the liquid for the containment behaviour. Last, an OpenModelica-containmentFOAM coupling scheme is under implementation to represent the specific safety features of Design-II, such as the pressure suppression system.

KEYWORDS

SMR, CFD, containmentFOAM, two-phase flow, system code coupling

1. INTRODUCTION

Ten years after the Fukushima Daiichi accident, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) foresees for the first time a positive tendency on the potential growth of nuclear power capacity worldwide [1], a tendency consolidated by the most optimistic net-zero scenarios of other institutions such as the International Energy Agency (IEA) [2], and the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) [3]. In this last scenario,

the NEA foresees the installation of up to 400 GW of Small Modular Reactors (SMR), which are expected to occupy a central role in the coming years. Among all the concepts being considered, the Light Water SMRs (LW-SMRs) have higher chances of being developed in the short term, which should ease the licensing of these advanced concepts. Indeed, the identification of Severe Accident (SA) sequences¹ is a key step towards the licensing of SMRs, as those are needed to inform level 4 (severe accident management) and level 5 (off-site emergency response) of the defence-in-depth concept [4,5].

The Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project [6,7], coordinated by ENEA (Italy) launched in 2022 goes all the way from the identification of potential postulated SA sequences to the evaluation of the extension of the emergency planning zones. Notably, SASPAM-SA investigates the applicability of the know-how for large-LWRs to LW-SMR, with a focus on identifying potential phenomenological differences of relevance for postulated SA progressions and the ability of the SA codes to replicate the expected phenomena. The project is currently ongoing and the results for the Work Package 2, coordinated by KIT (Germany) and focused on the identification of sequences, are summarised in [8].

The LW-SMR studied in SASPAM-SA are not replicas of any concept being explored for commercial deployment. Instead, the evaluations are performed using generic concepts with representative features for a range of designs². The so-called Design-I in SASPAM-SA features a generic integral Pressure Water Reactor (i-PWR) of about 60 MWe embedded in a metallic containment submerged in a pool. The Design-I does not have a safety injection system and relies on a global natural circulation loop for the long-term removal of the decay heat. The Design-II consists of a generic integral i-PWR of about 300 MWe and a large dry spherical containment. Though also fully relying on passive safety, the design includes a full range of safety systems typically used in advanced LWRs: high- and low-pressure safety injections, a pressure suppression system for the containment pooling, and a pool with a heat exchanger for decay heat removal³. Examples of postulated SA sequences applicable for both generic designs are discussed in [4] and [6].

The focus of this paper will be on the large dry containment of Design-II, which will be simulated using containmentFOAM [11]. containmentFOAM is an open-source CFD package based on OpenFOAM [12] that is specifically tailored towards the needs of containment SA analysis for conventional large PWRs. Accordingly, containmentFOAM used a single-phase approach where the liquid phase inside the containment was treated as a passive scalar and simply removed from the simulation domain when it is condensed at the walls. Most of the code developments aimed to obtain a detailed characterisation of the multi-species gas phase heat and mass transport phenomena of the containment. This was accomplished by adding specific models for wall condensation, turbulent buoyancy-driven flows, aerosol deposition, engineering systems, etc. The accidental sequences of LW-SMRs bring scenarios with distinct characteristics, and therefore the general modelling approach of containmentFOAM needs to be re-evaluated for its applicability.

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied. More detailed information's in [4].

² It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition.

³ Considering the selected passive systems and the generic SMR features, a generic IRIS-SMR type has been considered as reference for this analysis (no proprietary data have been used); therefore, the main geometric information has been determined by scaling the data available from the SPES-3 facility, by engineering evaluation or public general data available from the IRIS reactor [9].

This article is structured into three main sections. First, the containment thermal-hydraulics of the different phases of the available Design-II sequences is described in detail. The evaluation of the scenarios is used as a basis for the identification of containmentFOAM modelling upgrades to tackle the expected phenomenology. Afterwards, chapter 3 presents a preliminary validation of the domain decomposition approach and code coupling scheme used to model the containment and Pressure Suppression System (PSS) of Design-II by coupling containmentFOAM and OpenModelica [13]. Last, a summary of the insights of the work performed so far, and an outlook will be given as a conclusion.

2. TAILORING containmentFOAM FOR LW-SMR SCENARIOS

As briefly introduced above, one of the main objectives of the SASPAM-SA project is to evaluate the applicability of the know-how from large LWRs to LW-SMRs. Specifically, for containmentFOAM, this evaluation is aimed at identifying the features of the code tailoring to simulate conventional large PWRs that may limit its ability to address LW-SMR scenarios. The evaluation is performed before developing a containment model for the Design-II of SASPAM-SA. The anticipated detailed analysis of the foreseen technical-scale application drives the prioritisation of the code development needs. The evaluation has been performed on the basis of previous publications [10,14] and the ongoing work in SASPAM-SA [8]. The description of a generic sequence for Design-II is used to list the principal development needs of containmentFOAM. Therefore, only the most relevant thermal-hydraulic differences for conventional large PWRs and the LW-SMR will be addressed, referring the reader to the original references to have a complete description of the transient. The generic accidental sequence is separated into four phases represented in Figure 1, three for the Design Basis Accident (DBA) consisting of the Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) break and one for a hypothetical postulated SA. Figure 1 separates the containment free volume between the drywell and the Reactor Cavity (RC), also representing the main passive safety systems: Pressure Suppression System (PSS), Automatic Depressurization System (ADS), Long-term Gravity Make-up System (LGMS), Quench Tank (QT), and Emergency Borated Tanks (EBT).

Generally, the accident evolution is driven by the pressure differences of three connected “systems”: the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) – P_1 , the Drywell – P_2 , and the PSS – P_3 . The four phases of the transient highlighted in Figure 1 reflect the principal flow transport processes to/from the containment for different pressure differences. A brief description of each phase with its main modelling challenges is given below:

Pressure suppression ($P_1 \gg P_2 > P_3$)

The first phase in Figure 1 shows the situation immediately after the DVI line break. The break will produce a rapid release of superheated liquid that will flash in the containment atmosphere. Design-II, as well as Design-I and several other LW-SMRs, has as a design target to equalise the pressure of the RPV (P_1) and the Drywell (P_2) as fast as possible. Therefore, a second flow path from the RPV is open via the ADS-1. The pressure increase in the containment will induce a pressure difference, allowing the flow transport from the Drywell (P_2) to the PSS (P_3), as shown in Figure 1. The steam purged into the PSS will be condensed in the subcooled pool, limiting the pressure increase in the Drywell. The backpressure at the PSS, whose gas space is connected to the LGMS, will determine the flow from the Drywell to the PSS. Since the PSS is dimensioned to condense all the steam while remaining subcooled, the pressure increase in the PSS will be characterised by the accumulation of Non-Condensable Gases (NCGs) in its gas space.

The first challenge for the modelling basis of containmentFOAM, arising from the chain of events described above, is related to the physics of the wall condensation. For the range of pressures expected in conventional large reactors, the presence of NCGs in the boundary layer is the main thermal resistance to delimit the condensation rates [15,16]. However, as Design-II is designed to accelerate the pressure equalisation, the pressure peaks in the containment can be in a range between 9 bar and 14 bar [10,14]. The larger steam concentrations associated with these higher pressures, in other LW/SMRs [5] will induce a film-wise

condensation regime [17] where the main thermal resistance to delimit the condensation rates is the liquid film. This motivates the need for an extension of the wall condensation models and the validation matrix of containmentFOAM, which is currently ongoing.

Figure 1. Representation of three phases of a DBA (DVI break) and a SA in the Design-II

PSS reverse flow ($P_1 \approx P_2 < P_3$)

The PSS reverse flow represents the second phase in Figure 1. The maximum pressure reached in the drywell for a DBA happens at the same time as the pressure equalisation with the RPV ($P_1 \approx P_2$). After that, the pressures of RPV and Drywell start decreasing again by the combined effect of the core cooling systems and wall condensation, respectively. However, these cooling processes do not affect the PSS and LGMS (P_3). At a certain point of the transient, the higher pressure at the PSS will be large enough to push back water from the PSS to the drywell.

Similarly to the pressure suppression phase, the pressure differences drive the succession of events foreseen in the Design-II safety concept. Remarkably, the pressures of the three different systems are strongly linked, and the mass and energy transfer processes controlling the evolution of the pressure at each separate system influence the others. Therefore, the simulation of the primary, the containment or the safety system with different codes, a typical approach for conventional PWRs, would have stronger limitations for the LW-SMRs.

While the coupled simulation of RPV, drywell, and PSS has a clear added value for the representativeness of the calculations, it comes with a significant additional bargain in terms of computational cost. Hence, for the technical scale application foreseen in this work, it is not practical to use the same level of detail to simulate all the systems. To have the flexibility for cleverly deciding where to put the detail, i.e. to enable multi-scale calculations, arises as an essential feature for containmentFOAM. Consequently, a coupling scheme to facilitate multi-scale calculations using the Modelica [18] programming language for representing the system domain is under development. The coupling scheme and preliminary validation of the system-code-like modelling of the PSS will be described in the following chapter.

Stable cooling ($P_1 \approx P_2 \approx P_3$)

The third phase in Figure 1 represents the status of the containment after reaching a stable long-term cooling. The water transported from the PSS to the RC is above the break elevation. At this moment, the second phase of the ADS (ADS-2) would ensure the equalisation of the pressure of Drywell and RPV. In a DBA, the water from the RC will enter the RPV by the additional pressure of the water column. The steam produced at the RPV will be released to the Drywell by the ADS-2, condensed at the metallic walls, and injected back into the RPV, closing the cooling loop.

The relevance of considering the presence of liquid phase in the containment is evident in the third phase in Figure 1. Apart from the relevance of confirming that the water is transferred to the cavity and reaches a higher elevation of the break, it occupies more than 10% of the containment free volume, a value that can get close to 50% in other LW-SMR [5]. Therefore, the space occupied by the liquid phase will have a significant impact when calculating the containment pressure. The larger relevance of the liquid phase motivates the upgrade of the current multi-species single-phase solver of containmentFOAM with a two-phase volume of fluid approach [19].

Severe accident

When it is postulated that some of the safety systems briefly mentioned above do not comply with their safety function (through the postulated failure of correspondent valves to open), the core cooling may be compromised. In this case, a hypothetical core degradation may induce the release of up to 480 kg of H₂ to the containment [10]. Commonly, the SA may happen when the postulated failure of safety systems does not allow long-term stable cooling. For example, in the fourth phase in Figure 1, the water level at the cavity stays below the break location. The conditions of this scenario, while there is no significant flow transport between PRV, drywell and PSS, would be within the modelling basis of the current version of containmentFOAM (v9). The presence of NCG would limit the condensation, and the presence of water and its mass and energy exchange with the gas phase could be easily modelled.

3. COUPLING Modelica AND containmentFOAM

The technical-scale application of CFD codes to reactor safety analysis has an intrinsic multi-scale nature. The characteristic lengths in the order of μm of relevant phenomena such as turbulence, homogeneous condensation, or the physics at the boundary layer are combined with convection loops or safety systems whose actuation can be represented with larger scales. As discussed in the previous section, the coupling of

the containment thermal-hydraulics and the passive safety system is stronger for LW-SMRs than for conventional large PWRs. Consequently, this chapter describes the ongoing work to support a multi-scale modelling approach by coupling containmentFOAM with simplified models of the safety systems using the Modelica language. The general features of the coupling scheme used in this work, which will be extended to simulate other components (PARs, heat exchangers, etc.), are described in a first subsection to later present the model of the PSS developed for simulating the Design-II. The preliminary validation for the PSS model based on the public information of PPOOLEX experiments in [20] is also described below.

3.1 Characteristics of the Coupling

The central feature of the coupling approach is the use of the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) 2.0 standard [21] for defining the exchange of information between containmentFOAM and the system-code-like model of the PSS. The model of the PSS was developed and exported as an executable simulator called Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU) using OpenModelica. The FMI is a standard extensively used in the automotive and aerospace industries that offers a clear and open interface whereby multiple parties can develop FMUs to be coupled with the same integral model. The three main characteristics to highlight for this coupling approach are as follows:

- The FMI standard and Modelica are aligned with the open-source nature of containmentFOAM. The foundational aim of Modelica was to unify the concepts of different languages designed to solve system of differential and algebraic equations with different purposes, designing a new open language to boost the collaboration between different fields [18]. The same applies to the FMI coupling, an open standard for the exchange of information between codes. Every simulation tool adapted to support the FMI standard can be straightforwardly coupled [21].
- Most of the coupling solutions in the nuclear industry are code specific, and usually require access to the source code of proprietary tools [22]. Contrary, as it is defined as a standard for the exchange of information, FMI compatibility is code agnostic.
- The combination of the previous two features gives a total modularity to the proposed coupling scheme. Different institutions can develop individual FMUs for different purposes, and those could be easily coupled to solve an integral problem thanks to the FMI standard.

At its current status, the coupling scheme uses a domain decomposition approach allowing the pressure-velocity coupling of uni-directional fluid flow. The system (“SYS”) and CFD models can exchange pressure, temperature, mass composition, and mass flow fields of the gas phase [13]. It uses a semi-implicit scheme with Picard-iterations for the time discretisation and allows: (i) several updates of the serial mapping of field values until reaching convergence (see Figure 2, left), and (ii) for sub-cycling on the FMU side, if only an explicit forward Euler solver is available for the Modelica model. Parallel processing and simulation restart features are also included in the coupling. Its implementation is a “native” extension of the main containmentFOAM solver loop, utilising only the FMI Library [21] and the OpenFOAM-provided parallel MPI-based communication mechanisms.

The descriptions of the previous paragraph define the characteristics of the coupling within the six tiers proposed by [22] for couplings classification. As it is shown in [23], the implemented coupling scheme has been systematically verified to ensure numerical stability and conservativeness, and have not been included here for the sake of brevity.

Figure 2. Sketch of the main characteristics of the proposed coupling scheme (Source [18])

3.2 Preliminary validation using the PPOOLEX MIX-04 test

The preliminary validation selected for this paper aims to showcase the performance of the described coupling in a scenario close to the technical scale application foreseen in SASPAM-SA. Specifically, the transport of the gas mixture from the drywell to the PSS during the pressure suppression phase (see Figure 1). To reproduce the pressure-based coupling using the multi-species single phase solver of containmentFOAM, a simple model of the PSS was programmed and exported as an FMU using OpenModelica. The model of the PSS is based on the ThermoPower library [24]. The FMU models the PSS as a single node where the liquid and gas spaces are separated.

The temperature, pressure and mass flow rate flowing through the vent lines are calculated by containmentFOAM and averaged to be compatible with the 0D approach of the FMU. Since the PSS is expected to have tens of degrees of subcooling during the transient, all the steam reaching the PSS is immediately condensed in the liquid phase of the FMU after releasing its latent heat. The non-condensable gases coming from the drywell bypass the pool and accumulate in the gas space.

The preliminary validation for the coupling scheme and the FMU is based on the MIX-04 experiment performed at PPOOLEX, a test facility designed and constructed by the Lappeenranta University of Technology [20]. The facility was conceived to investigate BWR issues, and therefore the PPOOLEX vessel is split into a drywell and a wetwell connected by a pipe, as indicated in Figure 3. The analogy between the PPOOLEX configuration and the Design-II containment is straightforward, being the drywell of PPOOLEX equivalent to the PSS of the Design-II. As it is indicated in the scheme in Figure 3, the drywell of PPOOLEX is modelled with containmentFOAM and the wetwell with the FMU developed to simulate the PSS. The interface of the domain-decomposition coupling is realized at the exit of the pipe connecting drywell and wetwell using the FMI standard.

Figure 3. Sketch of the strategy used to model the PPOOLEX facility with OpenModelica & containmentFoam

The MIX-04 test is part of a series of experiments [20] investigating different flow regimes for the direct contact condensation process associated to the injection of steam to a subcooled pool. Specifically, the key parametric change is the steam mass flow rate, which may induce the development of a thermal stratification within the pool. As it is shown in Figure 4, the steam injection in MIX-04 can be split into three phases. At the beginning of the experiment, a relatively large flow rate is used to push the NCGs to the wetwell and to heat up the metallic walls of the vessel until reaching the thermal equilibrium with the injected steam. In the second phase, the steam flow rate is reduced for a period of 4000 seconds to increase later to 350 g/s in the third phase. The analysis of the liquid level and average pool temperature data proved that the actual steam injection rate during the stratification phase ('Flow correction-EXP' in Figure 4) was lower than the nominal value ('Flowmeter-EXP' in Figure 4).

The impact of the different flow rates on the water pool can be understood from the experimental recordings plotted with markers in Figure 5 (experimental data and simulation results showed together due to space limitations). During the first phase, the pool temperature increase was below 5 °C, and the main phenomenon was the pressure increase produced by the accumulation of the NCGs in the wetwell. The second phase is characterised by the pool stratification, which has not been represented in the graphs. The pool average temperature is a better figure of merit for the comparisons with the simulation results, but the difference between the maximum and minimum temperatures recorded in the pool reached 25 °C. The third phase of the experiments is characterised by the faster increase in the pool average temperature driven by the higher steam flow rate. The chugging induced by the larger flow rates homogenised the pool temperature.

Figure 4. Boundary conditions for steam injection in the drywell.

Figure 5. Comparison of experimental data and simulation results.

As indicated from the beginning, the validation exercise is preliminary, and there are several simplifications to consider before describing the simulation results:

- The FMU model uses a 0D approach where the liquid phase is characterised by a single temperature. Therefore, it is not possible to model pool stratification with this approach. This limitation was accepted because the priority of the validation was to demonstrate the stability of the pressure/velocity coupling. Indeed, for the technical scale application of the Design-II SMR, the pressure increase is driven by the transport of NCGs, not by the pool heating.
- The FMU is currently under development, and the version used for this work did not have a complete implementation of all the physics of the problem. The two main limitations to consider are the (i) non-inclusion of the heat transfer between the drywell and the wetwell, (ii) and the lack of an evaporation/condensation model for the liquid/gas interface. Again, it is important to highlight that these limitations affect the simulation of PPOOLEX but not the foreseen technical scale application, where there is no heat transfer from the PSS to the Drywell.
- For the sake of simplicity, the wall condensation process and the heat capacity of the metallic walls were not considered in the containmentFOAM model for the drywell. Therefore, the steam injection rate was reduced during the first phase of the experiment, reducing the energy injected in the simulation domain according to the energy that would be absorbed by the walls. The reduced flow

steam flow rate used in containmentFOAM for the first phase of the experiment was shown in Figure 4. The steam flow rate reduction was equivalent to the energy needed to heat the metallic walls of the drywell (calculated by the wall thermocouples measurements)

Figure 5 presents the comparison of the simulations and the experimental results. The graph shows the pressure of the drywell, calculated with containmentFOAM, the gas pressure of the wetwell and an average temperature for the wetwell pool, both taken from the FMU (Modelica). The first thing to highlight on the simulations side is the stability and smooth convergence of the calculation. The simulation ran with a constant Courant number of 5, a time step of 0.012 seconds, and doing between 4 and 5 PIMPLE iterations each time step (approx. 500 s / day on 16 Xeon cores). Adding to the stable performance of the pressure coupling is its capability to qualitatively represent the evolution of PPOOLEX conditions. The fast pressurisation of the facility was driven by the accumulation of NCGs in the drywell, which was observed on both the CFD and FMU sides. The simulation also reproduced the slower pressurisation in the second and third phases of the transient driven by the facility's temperature increase.

The quantitative deviations between the experimental measurements and the simulation results shown in Figure 5 are related to the limitations of the modelling approach listed in the previous bullet points. The predicted pressure was approximately 0.25 bar lower than the experimental recordings, which is explained by the non-inclusion of the heat transfer between the drywell and the wetwell. This heat transfer from the drywell (approximately at 130 °C) to the wetwell (initially at 20 °C) would increase the temperature, and thus the pressure, of the gas space of the wetwell. However, since this heat transfer process does not have a significant impact on the quantity of energy arriving at the pool, the simulations showed a solid quantitative agreement for the increase of the pool's average temperature.

The work to consolidate the results of this preliminary validation is currently ongoing. The coupling scheme allows multiple connections between an FMU and the CFD model. Therefore, the implementation of the heat transfer from the drywell to the wetwell is relatively simple. Furthermore, the FMU will be updated to include the free surface evaporation and the heat losses of the wetwell. Last, the CFD model will be modified to simulate the wall condensation in the Drywell, where the thermal-hydraulic (almost pure steam) has similar characteristics to the blowdown of the i-PWR Design-II SMR that will be simulated in SASPAM-SA. Yet, the stability and qualitative behaviour of the pressure-based coupling scheme have been proven to be a successful proof of concept for these further developments.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The phenomenological differences between the SA scenarios of LW-SMRs and the conventional large PWR (those used as the reference scenarios for the development of containmentFOAM) motivated a re-evaluation of the traditional modelling approach of containmentFOAM. The knowledge acquired by participating in SASPAM-SA allowed the prioritisation of the code developments needed to use containmentFOAM for LW-SMRs simulations. Essentially, these developments should help to handle the characteristic stronger pressure coupling between containment, primary, and safety systems and to consider the more prominent role of two-phase issues in the unfolding of an accident. Besides, the general validation matrix of the code should be extended to consider other flow regimes, such as the film-wise wall condensation.

The work described in this article focused on the need to represent the stronger pressure coupling between the containment and the passive safety systems. A technical scale application for the SMR Design-II evaluated in SASPAM-SA requires the use of multi-fidelity simulation tools, where the modellers should carefully choose the level of detail to represent each part of the problem. The multi-fidelity modelling frameworks have been enabled by developing a coupling framework for containmentFOAM and OpenModelica using the FMI standard. The solution is open source, transparent, and uses a well-defined framework that is compatible with any other FMI-compatible code.

The coupling scheme is in continuous development and is currently under validation. Yet, it has proved its stability in a demanding domain-decomposition pressure-coupling to model the PPOOLEX MIX-04 experiment. Besides, the simulations reproduced the qualitative behaviour of an experiment with relevant common features with the foreseen technical scale application. Still, advancing the preliminary validation of this article to a solid final validation matrix based on PPOOLEX experiments requires additional work along different lines. So far, the primary phenomena for the foreseen technical scale application, the transport of non-condensable gases and the steam condensation in the PSS, showed a promising quantitative and qualitative agreement with the experimental results.

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